

NIST/EFA Mapping Table 20260216

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Table 1 – NIST AI RMF to Ethical Functionality without Agency (EFA) Elements

NIST AI RMF Function / Sub-function	Description in NIST RMF	Corresponding EFA/E7 or RoF Element	How It Aligns / Addresses the Requirement
Govern 1.1, 2.2	Policies prohibit AI moral authorship; humans retain decision ownership	EFA core thesis: explicit prohibition on AI moral authorship; permanent human decision ownership	Full alignment — EFA enforces this at the architectural level
Map 3	Identify and document risks, including bias	RoF parallel 8-LLM peer review with $\geq 6/8$ consensus thresholds	Measurable, reproducible bias detection via multi-model consensus
Measure 2.10–2.13	Assess performance, bias, drift, robustness	RoF SHA-256 token-level audit trails + drift detection	Provides verifiable, tamper-proof evidence of drift/bias
Manage 4	Implement risk treatments, controls	Zero-code containment layer (~\$40/month on consumer LLMs)	Dramatically lowers barriers for small/large entities; deployable today

NIST concept paper: <https://www.nccoe.nist.gov/news-insights/new-concept-paper-identity-and-authority-software-agents>

The five areas in the concept paper (identification, authorization, delegation, logging, data flows) are all covered in E7:

Identification/delegation → Layer 3 (control handoffs) + Layer 5 (policy mapping).

Authorization/logging → Layer 5 (constraints) + Layer 7 (audit trails).

The behavior gap discussed by Josh Woodruff ([Joshua Woodruff | LinkedIn](#)) and others is precisely what Layer 6 (runtime enforcement) + RoF (drift/uncertainty monitoring) close.